

Engaging Southeast Asia: The political economy of regional leadership competition between Japan and China

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ABSTRACT

Regionalization in East Asia has drastically arisen the past two decades. Other than economic coordination, competition of regional leadership has been steering the direction of regional integration. In terms of finance, East Asian states have also established the Chiang Mai Initiative for regional monetary cooperation. In the trade sphere, free trade agreements have mushroomed after the millennium. In particular, special emphasis is given to the competition between Japan and China as this is considered as one of the main forces to push the regionalization drive forward. By comparing Japan and China's regional policy, this paper seeks to opens possibilities about the path, motivations and future opportunities for East Asian integration through a qualitative synthesis of opinion from experts, requirement from authorities and existing studies.

Keywords: *China, East Asia, Japan, regionalization*

I. INTRODUCTION

East Asian regionalism has been one of the most significant cases of global economic integration in the past few years. The "East Asian Community" had been the regional consensus in 2007. The ASEAN Economic Community was expected to be established by 2015. The China-Japan-South Korea Free Trade Agreement is still undergoing negotiation, in spite of unsolved territorial disputes. Without reverse waves, there would be no doubt that East Asia will be the single biggest economic block in the world in the near future. Foreseeing this, some experts start to deliver warnings of East Asian regionalism. Functional integration in the regional level is still underdeveloped. Geographical diversity, state sizes, and political rivalry remain an obstacle for

robust institutional capacity (Ravenhill, 2009). The core functions of regionalism, trade and finance are not ready to compete with Europe and North America. Apparently, it is time to scrutinize the progress and development of East Asian regionalism.

Since the Asian Financial Crisis, East Asian countries started to recognize the necessity for regional economic coordination. The next decade, East Asian countries reached diverse progress regarding financial coordination and free trade negotiations. On finance, the Chiang Mai Initiative (CMI) is considered as a milestone of regional monetary cooperation. In the trade sphere, free trade agreements (FTAs) also flourished after the millennium. FTAs and financial coordination

are derivative phenomena of globalization. By May 2003, over 265 FTAs were reported to the World Trade Organization (WTO) wherein 138 FTAs were governed under WTO in January 1995. Over 190 are currently in force; another 60 are believed to be operational although not yet reported. However, in East Asia, diffusion of FTAs is relatively lagged. In November 2001, China and ASEAN leaders agreed to establish a China-ASEAN Free Trade Area (CAFTA). In 2005, Japan followed suit to reach similar agreements with ASEAN countries. The 1997 Financial Crisis has proven to be a turning point for regionalism in Asia. But there are limited explanations on why East Asian countries are late in the pursuit of regional integration, and on what motivations are necessary for East Asian countries to pursue cross-border financial coordination, and trade negotiations.

Higgott (1998) astutely observed the Asian Financial Crisis and said "the political manifestations of these events (the financial crises) will linger long after the necessary reforms have been introduced to return at least a semblance of economic normalcy to the region." There might be two meaning of Higgott's argument. Firstly, new regional institutional arrangements have to be established in wake of critical juncture. As the crisis has become the catalyst of financial and trade reform, exogenous impact may influence the logic of regional response. Secondly, as the Crisis is also political, regional countries will seek financial and trade policies based on different motivations and perceptions of existing situation. This perspective could be seen from sub-regional trade agreements being busily negotiated by Japan, South Korea, Singapore and other countries in East Asia. Alternatively, national responses could also be analyzed to discern the logic in disseminating financial and trade knowledge.

This paper aims to discuss probable answers to the core questions of national response to regionalism, and how these factors may influence the path to East Asian integration, focusing on a comparison of Japan and China's political economy as competition between these two countries is a probable catalyst for increased regionalization. We will see how cross-border financial coordination and FTA policies disseminate, how national

governments understand regionalization, and how idea and motivations contribute in adopting specific FTA policies. In Section II of the study, regionalization and FTA policy diffusion in East Asia are summarized. Two hypotheses of policy diffusion and a multidimensional definition of competition are presented. The Asian Financial Crisis will also be discussed as it served as the critical juncture for East Asian countries to recognize the importance of regional coordination in the financial sphere. Section III is dedicated to illustrating the way regional countries attempt to imitate the IMF arrangements and receive limited success in spite of their efforts. Section IV delves deeper and focuses on Japan and China by comparing their economic, political, and legal motivations in pursuit of FTAs. Section V concludes this article by consolidating information on how the diffusion and dissemination of financial and FTA policies possibly results in closer regionalization. It also reviews the competition for regional leadership between Japan and China, and the implications of this competition on further regionalization in East Asia.

II. THE EAST ASIAN PATTERN OF REGIONAL LEADERSHIP AND FTA POLICY DIFFUSION

Before the Asian Financial Crisis, the dissemination of FTA and financial collaboration in East Asia is lagged behind the progress of EU and NAFTA. Yet, the financial crisis provoked great sense of regional consciousness. As argued by Acharya, regional countries started to recognize the necessity to strengthen regional organization in the wake of the Crisis (Acharya, 2004). Simmons, Dobbin and Garrett (2007) argued that one reason that could explain the rise of regional sense is the economic imperative of regional powers to keep competition. In order to keep regional economy afloat, regional powers would shoulder the role of stabilizing order and cooperate with regional countries to reshuffle existing organizations. In the 1990s, East Asian regional countries engaged in collective pursuit of economic liberalization. Whether resisted or accepted, regional countries accelerated domestic economic reform and deregulated financial market. During this process, regional powers were considered referral to legitimize domestic reform (Dobbin, Simmons

& Garrett, 2007) . The emulation process triggered a series of policy diffusion. Hall (1993) indicated that the regional policy paradigms may incrementally forge and offer cognitive maps to influence policymakers by “a framework of ideas and standards that specifies not only the goals of policy and the kind of instruments, but also the very nature of the problems they are meant to be addressing.” Further, the universe of knowledge of regionalization would have significantly clout an idea. The process of greater regional integration on multilayer agendas, for instance, Acharya emphasized that the regionalist discourses would eventually develop and in turn reshape the process of region building (Acharya, 1997). Katzenstein and Okawara (1993) have come to conclude similarly, pertaining to national security.

Apparently, diffusion of policies takes place when regional powers’ actions generate externalities for others. Simmons, Dobbin and Garret further contended that, in trade and financial market, rival regional powers’ policies that attract international capital would compel others to follow suit as well. It follows that the international competition may make regional powers pursue regional policy in similar ways (Simmons, Dobbin & Garret, 2006).

It is worthy to know the epidemic effects of regional powers’ policy. According to MacIntyre, Pempel and Ravenhill (2008), Southeast Asian countries emulated Japan after the Asian Financial Crisis, for policy innovation in adopting regional standards in order to effectively enhance the attractiveness of domestic markets. Generally, according to Dent (2008), regional powers competing for leadership come with certain behavior and benefits. Firstly, regional leadership has to provide public goods that include a stable and secured environment, sustainable development, and reduction of the region’s poverty levels. Secondly, regional leadership has to resolve collective action problems. When negotiating regional integration regulations, regional leadership has to communicate between groups of states and manage agenda in order to make all member states compromise on agreements. Beyond the two roles, regional leadership also has to lead the regional community-building process and champion the interests of the regional

community in the global level.

Collective policy adoption in the regional level is based on the efforts of regional leadership. The most conspicuous sectors are financial coordination and FTA policies. When regional leaders start to initiate cross-national policy networks that are crucial to disseminate policy knowledge, governments are committed to engage in negotiating as many preferential financial and trade agreements as possible with little concern about sequencing. Governments also take a homogeneous position through recognizing international standard rules that closely mirror those of reference countries.

Currently, students of East Asian study mostly agree that regional leadership primarily concentrates on the ‘national-level’ activities of China and Japan. Through constellation of governmental agencies of either Japan or China, researches indicate that domestic politics play a key part in determining the outlooks of what both Japan and China have on regional or international leadership issues. From a macro perspective, other than Japan and China, there are also relevant actors in different policy areas. Of course, the prospect for regional leadership in East Asia is more complex than what has been mentioned above. Extra-regional actors, including U.S., Australia, New Zealand, and India sometimes complicate analyses on specific issues. It is also possible that a regional leadership structure based on China and Japan may not be desirable for the regional collective as a whole, because regional states incrementally voice their demands in the global and extra-regional levels and have anticipated less on regional collectives.

Concerning financial and trade integration, regional countries act differently as they take a realist perspective. Domestic politics is still the key of regional policy. Preferences of bureaucrats play an important role on regional policy. Business and economic bureaucrats are concerned with investment and trade diversion. Politicians and diplomats focus on the notions of international finance and trade policies. In order to maximize relative/competitive advantage in the financial and trade area, countries adopt financial and trade policies selectively with special attention to counterpart choices, market

access commitments, and rule-making in FTAs which should be beneficial in creating national competitive advantage. Governments also take a "heterogeneous position to quest FTAs with a distinct package of investment and trade rules.

In the initial stage of regional integration, countries may perceive lenient pressure of financial and trade competition and rarely rank regionalization on the top of policy making list. The main motivations for countries to adopt financial and trade policies with special orientation for greater regional participation are generally related to the appeals of business and economic bureaucrats. As the process of regionalization intensifies, a higher degree of rule-making is realized, countries perceive competitive pressure and strategically position themselves in the regional finance and trade blocs.

This article may not provide a clear picture for the development of East Asian regional leadership. A possible speculation, the development of financial and trade market, still has to be based on evidence in exercising regional leadership in East Asia. In a broad sense, Japan would continue to play an indirect role in cooperating with ASEAN countries based on its official development aids and economic power. China would cash on its rise of political and economic strengths and declare the leadership in a more assertive way. In addition, China should also prefer a regional framework that excludes the influence of extra-regional power, especially U.S. and India. The definition of regional membership would continuously be a central arena for Japan and China to struggle on. The different nature of Japan and China's regional approaches to lead may sometimes make it awkward to compare the two countries. Yet, it would make more sense to work on individual cases before jumping into a general theory or model.

III. REGIONAL FINANCIAL INITIATIVES

The East Asian financial crisis of 1997-1998 provides several valuable lessons for East Asian regional integration. Many economic, academic and government policy makers saw the Asian Financial Crisis as a wake-up call to libertarian market policy. Governments in this region were incapable to govern global capital flow and fend

off vicious attacks of speculators. The financial institutions had to reform. The capital market had to be supervised and regulated following the international standards (Wang, 2003). Except China and Japan, the Asian Financial Crisis demonstrated vulnerability of small and open emerging markets (Manupipatpong, 2002). Early in 1995, a number of economists began to warn Southeast Asian countries about the possibility of suffering a Latin American style of financial crisis. In 1996, IMF and World Bank also delivered alert to the governments of Thailand, Malaysia, and other countries about the risk of respective financial markets. However, these warnings were generally snubbed (Krugman, 1998).

After export slowdown occurred in 1997, the real estate that bubbled in Thailand soon collapsed. On July 2, Thailand gave in to the pressures and floated the baht. Then, a series of currency speculation against other regional countries followed. Malaysia, Indonesia, and the Philippines were all hit in the first wave (Krugman, 1998).

Without precedent experience of international finance coordination, Southeast Asian countries had meager institutional support to act collectively. The slack institutional arrangements of Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) were proven incapable to lead regional countries in fighting against financial catastrophe (Suh, 2002). Some regional organizations were introduced and established in the 1990, including the ASEAN Free Trade Agreement for trade liberalization, APEC, ASEM, and the Manila Framework Group. But none had ever reached high levels of institutionalization of the financial sector (Goto, 2002). The Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC), established in 1989, was considered promising to reach sensible solution for Southeast Asian countries. Under the institutional design of multilateral framework and strong influence from the U.S., APEC did not deliver a solid package for financial rescue.

Japanese Finance Minister Hirishi Mitsuzuka proposed to establish an Asian Monetary Fund (AMF) that would provide sufficient liquidity (emergency capital) which could quickly mobilize a country in urgent need of foreign currency to forestall speculative attacks on the region's

currencies and to institutionalize financial cooperation in the region. The Japanese proposal was considered as an institutional innovation to imitate the IMF framework with the possibility of exchange rate coordination which is similar to European Exchange Rate Mechanism (ERM) (Castellano, 2000; Chalongphob, 2000). Many Southeast Asian countries strongly supported this proposal. Malaysian Prime Minister Mahathir Mohamad tabled the AMF initiative again at the Asian Summit in the World Economic Forum (WEF) held in Singapore, with expectation that AMF was established as an East Asian monetary cooperation mechanism. The AMF received mixed reactions, however. While most countries in East Asia welcomed a regional finance cooperation mechanism, U.S., EU and IMF, on the other hand, seriously opposed on the grounds that it would threaten the stability of the global financial system, by weakening the IMF's voice in promoting structural adjustments in recipient countries and by aggravating a serious moral hazard problem. Consequently, the AMF proposal was turned down at the Fifth Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation Meeting (APEC) in Manila (Park & Wang, 2003).

In 1998, the second ASEAN Plus Three (APT) Summit was held in Hanoi, Vietnam. China proposed establishing the APT Finance Ministers Deputies Meeting (FMDM), the first convention occurred in March 1999, and then the first Finance Ministers Meeting (FMM) in the following month held with the ADB Annual Meeting in Manila. The third APT Summit held in November 1999 at Manila marked a watershed in the development of financial regionalism in Asia. Besides the "Joint Statement on East Asia Cooperation," China insisted on the significance of strengthening the APT financial process. The Chinese proposal was supported by other participants and was agreed to regularize the APT's FMM arrangement (Hamanaka, 20085).

Following the discussion among high rank financial officials of APT countries, the Chiang Mai Initiative (CMI) was agreed at the second APT FMM held in May 2000 in Chiang Main, Thailand. At the core of the CMI arrangement was a region-wide system of bilateral currency swap arrangements among APT countries. It comprised a series of new regional economic surveillance and policy

dialogue mechanism. In October 1998 the Japanese government proposed a framework called "A New Initiative to Overcome the Asian Currency Crisis," also known as the New Miyazawa Initiative (NMI), aimed at providing a package of financial support totaling US\$30 billion. In fact, there was a demand for such funding from Asian countries in order to support corporate debt restructuring, strengthen social safety nets, stimulate the economy, and address the credit crunch. The United States and the IMF supported this initiative, owing to its bilateral nature, compared with the previous proposal that attempted to achieve cooperation on a multilateral basis.

Under the NMI scheme, Japan signed bilateral CSAs with South Korea and Malaysia in January and July 1999. CSAs were integrated in CMI by expanding the existing ASEAN Swap Arrangement (ASA) to include all ASEAN countries and a network of bilateral swap and repurchase agreement facilities among ASEAN countries, China, Japan and South Korea as a "firewall" against future financial crises (Wang & Woo, 2002). CMI did not only promote the exchange of consistent and timely data and information on capital flows, it also established a system of pooled reserves that central banks could draw upon to buy time when their currencies come under speculative attack (Lin & Rajan, 2001). An early warning system was established to enhance the ability in providing sufficient and timely financial stability.

Table 1
Bilateral swap arrangements under CMI (as of October 2002)

	Currencies	Maximum drawing
Japan & China	Yen-yuan remimbi	US\$ 3.0 billion equivalent
Japan&S. Korea	US dollar-won	US\$ 7.0 billion*
Japan & Singapore	US dollar-Singapore dollar	Under negotiation
China & Malaysia	US dollar-ringgit	US\$ 1.5 billion
China & S. Korea	Yuan renminbi-won	US\$ 2.0 billion equivalent
S. Korea & Philippines	US dollar-peso	Under negotiation
S. Korea & Thailand	US dollar-baht	US\$ 1.0 billion

Source: Ministry of Finance, Japan, 28 Mar 2002, and other country-specific webpages.

*Including a dollar-won swap arrangement of US\$ 5 billion and a dollar-ringgit swap arrangement of US\$ 2.5 billion from the New Miyazawa Initiative.

Beyond CMI efforts, significant progress was proceeding as well. The ASEAN Task Force on "ASEAN currency and Exchange Rate Mechanism" was established in March 2001. Additional impetus to this work was supported by the Kobe Research Project, which was an initiative of consultation mechanism comprising of the Asia-Europe Finance Ministers group. Under the Kobe Research Project a large number of studies were contributed by institutions and individual experts in Asia and Europe to further enhance monetary and financial cooperation (Rana, 2002).

By September 2005, the CMI system operated on a US\$54.5 billion total, and by May 2007 this had risen to US\$82.5 billion based on 16 bilateral agreements. Originally, as series of bilateral currency swap agreements among regional financial authorities, in broad terms, the CMI is a type of an expansion of ASA, aimed at providing countries facing the possibility of a liquidity shortage with additional short-term hard currencies. It encompasses all ASEAN countries, as well as China, Japan and Korea. This expansion of the ASA is the first step to put CMI effective. The CMI appeared to have been well received by IMF and U.S. At a press conference by Horst Kohler in Prague (September 20, 2000; Hamanaka, 2008), the new IMF Managing Director expressed support for AMF and other regional initiatives as long as they were complementary and not competitive with the IMF approach (Ross, 2001; Benassy-Quere, 1999).

IV. A COMPARISON OF JAPAN AND CHINA'S TRADE POLICIES AND MOTIVATIONS IN PURSUIT OF FTAS

East Asian countries were latecomers of free trade policies. When regionalism re-emerged as a preferred economic policy in the 1980s and 1990s, East Asian countries were relatively lagged behind in terms of formal political institutionalization of regional organizations. Political rivalry and security concerned between China and Japan are telling factors which delayed the progress in diffusing regional trade policies. After the Asian Financial Crisis, China moved actively to embrace regionalism and subsequently stimulated Japan to accelerate bilateral negotiations on economic partnership agreements. In the first decade

of the millennium, the FTA boom became the conspicuous phenomena in East Asia. Motivations behind the scene of China and Japan's pursuit in FTA negotiations are more political and legal than economic. Therefore, the logic to adopt FTA policies closely follows the competition hypothesis.

As for economic motivation, both China and Japan have different interests in pursuing FTAs. It is generally believed that China's rapid growth of exports is based on their plenty and cheap labor resource. FTAs are most effective in lowering tariffs and substantially reducing the costs of both exports and imports. For China's old-fashioned command enterprises, FTAs are considered to be a chance of enhancing the efficiency and productivity. China also attempted to use FTAs to make good use of ROOs. Even though WTO is not a shield for China to avoid impacts of ROOs on its vital exports, China can win better deals when negotiating ROOs based on its market power. Japan has a very different economic interest from China, however. Since the 1980s, Japanese business already extended their reach to Asian markets. Export was considered as the "life line" of Japanese economy. FTAs were deemed essential to maintain the competitive presence of Japanese multinationals in the region. The past decade, Japan diverted attention to bilateral FTAs with the largest ASEAN countries (Pekkanen, 2005). FTAs are important vehicles that facilitate Japan to build production networks and regional export platforms in ASEAN countries and to keep up with the competition from Chinese products. As China incrementally transforme itself from the "world factory" to the "world market," the Japanese business community also began to demand preferential trade negotiations with its largest trading partners, say China, U.S., and EU.

If we consider China as another candidate in competing for regional leadership, China's political logic in seeking FTAs is no less important than the economic one. As a major power, China's FTA strategy needs to serve the political goals in order to enhance its influence in the international political economy and expand its political and security space. Therefore, China makes FTAs an important tool for both economic as well as political diplomacy. For example, China signed

bilateral preferential agreements with Taiwan and Hong Kong based on the concept of Greater China Circle. China is also wary of Japan's effort in negotiating FTAs with its neighbors and imperative to reach key FTAs with ASEAN to break up the encirclement of Japan's FTA strategy. Japan's FTA policy is influenced by its diplomatic concern over the U.S. alliance, and security concern about China's rise in this region. As the U.S. wielded two wars in the Middle East, U.S. put gravity of Asia policy away from Japan. Therefore, Japan argues that U.S. should negotiate bilateral FTAs as the most effective economic means to strengthen the US-Japan alliance. On the other hand, Japan is engaged in the race for regional leadership since the Asian Financial Crisis. Further, national leaders of both countries perceived great pressure on domestic nationalism. Japan gradually defines China as a potential threat. Therefore, the initiative of former Prime Minister Hatoyama to form the "East Asian Community" could be considered as a policy innovation in striking the right balance with China.

Related to economic and political motivations, both China and Japan recognized the central importance of rule making in the multilateral framework. China has held a view that the existing international economic order is unfair and biased toward U.S. and EU. The concept of "harmonious world" also advocates a fair and rational international order. In G20 and WTO, China was always outspoken and opposed any linkage between trade and labor standards, and the use of environmental standards which limit China's rights of economic growth. Japan, however, has abandoned its previous attachment on a consensual approach for regional trade agreements like APEC. Japan's competitive legal strategy aimed to amend WTO provisions was deemed harmful to Japanese corporate interests. Both the Japanese government and business groups are also dissatisfied with multilateral antidumping code which is deemed by Japanese business as discriminatory treatment against Japanese business. Therefore, Japanese business interests identified FTAs as an opportunity to reform antidumping practices. Japan's legal competitive strategy has created an FTA approach different from both NAFTA and the Chinese trade

agreements. Japan's FTAs are more comprehensive in terms of issue scope and legalistic than Chinese FTAs, which are considered as brief and vague without formal dispute settlement mechanism. In FTA negotiations with ASEAN, Japan was more skillful in luring East Asia by offering agricultural concessions through the Early Harvest Program when establishing its cross-border FTA networks.

V. CONCLUSION

The diffusion and dissemination of financial and FTA policies in East Asian countries resulted in closer integration in the regional level. Differences in the stages of FTA development and environment make governments adopt policies through strategic calculation. As to the financial coordination in East Asia, institutional slackness of ASEAN way and political rivalry of major powers hesitate East Asian countries to establish complicated and capable institutional arrangements for cross-border financial coordination and supervision. In the critical juncture of the Asian Financial Crisis, East Asian countries proposed to imitate institutional design of IMF for regional countries to cooperate on monetary sphere. The AMF proposal invited opposition from U.S., EU and IMF for fear of the threatening stability of the global financial system. Japan, China and ASEAN countries compromised to create CMI by expanding the existing ASEAN Swap Arrangement as a firewall against future financial crisis. Diffusion of FTAs is a different story which is different from cross-border financial coordination. Since the late 1980s, Japanese multinationals and economic bureaucrats were considered as a strong lobby in promoting trade policy. In the post-Cold War period, Japan and Australia cooperated in establishing a regional trade bloc emulating the EU counterpart. Confined by regional environment, multilateral framework of APEC fails to copy the EU model. Instead, as different motivations, strategic calculation, and political rivalry will make APEC like talking shop (Ashiawa, 2004). Eventually China and Japan decided to seek FTAs through bilateral negotiation. On the late stage of FTA adoption, competition is the main driving force. Economic, political, and legal motivations are diverse between China and Japan. By juxtaposing China and Japan together,

FTA preference and pattern can be clearly discerned.

For large countries, such as China and Japan, the motivation for FTA policies includes both economic and noneconomic goals. China's choice of FTA partners is based on the strategic calculation that China could extend its space in international market. Japan provides being another case where politics is clearly relevant but market access, particularly being shut out of existing markets for Japanese industries, is also an important concern. At the same time, the Japanese governments is preoccupied with the country's uncompetitive domestic sectors, particularly agriculture, so that it cannot engage in FTAs with countries such as China and U.S. Pressures in political and legal competition are particularly central reasons for large states to engage in FTAs. China's increasingly active pursuit of FTAs both in East Asia and in Latin America has pressured the U.S. The dissemination of their own models of economic integration is also important for the large countries. The rivalry between Japan and China has pushed these two countries into active FTA negotiations within the Asian region, since both want not only to demonstrate their trade leadership but also to establish their own model of FTA standards. China offers a non-legalistic FTA model that features selective liberalization without clauses on issues like environment and labor standards. Japanese FTAs, named as Economic Partnership Agreements or EPAs, contrarily promote WTO-plus provisions including rules on investment and intellectual property.

Other perspectives could be explored to see how Japan and China extend regional leadership competition. Both countries possess their own particular kind of soft power resources, saying public diplomacy, ideas and norms, or other means. Recent years, soft power analysis already offered a different perspective from traditional approaches in studying leadership (Cohen & Chiu, 2013). Japan's limited success of translating its soft power into hard power and China's failure in containing Vietnam implicate the conspicuous limit of soft power in real politics. From the ideological perspective, regional leadership may enjoy soft power advantage to influence regional states and shape the agenda. Yet, the limited

success of soft power in East Asia suggests both Japan and China have to be more serious about soft power.

In the post-crisis period, there has been a significant change in the thinking of East Asian policymakers in developing a new regional financial and trade architecture by promoting self-help efforts. In this context the establishment of various regional organizations, the Chiang Mai Initiative and bilateral trade negotiations are efforts being made to expand regional integration. Yet, "political will" has to be developed for more concerted actions.

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